

SCHOOL HEAD'S INSTRUCTIONAL SUPERVISORY PRACTICES AND THE PERFORMANCE OF THE TEACHERS: A CORRELATIONAL STUDY

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School Head's Instructional Supervisory Practices and the Performance of the Teachers: A Correlational Study

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Abstract

The purpose of the research study "School Head's Instructional Supervisory Practices and the Performance of the Teachers: A Correlational Study" is to ascertain whether there is a connection between teachers' performance and school heads' instructional supervisory practices. To investigate the link between these two variables, the study uses a descriptive correlational research design. This study made use of a descriptive survey questionnaire to find out the level of school head's instructional supervisory practices and the teacher's performance in Secondary Public Schools of Monkayo West District. This investigation used two sets of questionnaires namely School Heads Instructional Supervisory Practices and Teachers Performance. The respondents were composed of 160 teachers coming from junior high school and senior high school. Using mean, pearson-r as the statistical tool, it was found out that the school head's instructional supervisory practices with its following indicators; resource provider, instructional specialist, curriculum specialist, learning facilitator, and school leader was described as often. This implies that the school head's instructional supervisory practices greatly contributed in determining the level of teachers' performances. The results revealed that teachers' performances with its following indicators; plans instructions, knowledge of the subject matter, and student engagement were described as often. This can be noted that the teachers' performance greatly affected in the level of school head's instructional supervisory practices. It was also revealed that there is significant relationship between school head's instructional supervisory practices and the performance of the teachers. Hence, it was concluded that it is important for school heads to continually update themselves on the best practices of instructional supervision. As a recommendation, Department of Education may continue to regularly train school heads, specifically those who are newly installed school heads on effective instructional supervisory practices. Curriculum Implementation Division Experts should consistently monitor and provide suggestions through professional training that will be conducted for the school heads. Teachers need to be trained regularly on the effective integration of technology in the classroom as well as in implementing their lessons in such a way that would foster better learning outcomes.

Keywords: *school head's instructional supervisory practices, teacher's performance, correlational*

Introduction

Supervision of instruction is crucial for achieving effective classroom instruction. It involves providing guidance, assistance, sharing ideas, facilitation, and resources to help teachers improve the learning situation and quality of learning in schools. According to Malonzo (2019), school heads play a vital role by providing professional support to teachers during discussions about conducting instructional supervision. This support is a key factor in implementing various supervisory practices effectively, ultimately leading to improved student achievement.

Effective teacher performance is crucial for the success of secondary education. However, research has highlighted persistent challenges in teacher performance at the secondary level. Studies have found issues such as teacher absenteeism, tardiness, and lack of instructional effectiveness in secondary schools. These problems in teacher performance can be attributed, in part, to the supervisory practices of school heads. Effective supervision by school heads has been identified as a key factor in enhancing teacher performance and improving student outcomes. Existing research suggests that school heads' supervisory practices, such as classroom observations, feedback, and professional development support, can have a significant impact on teachers' instructional skills, classroom management, and overall work performance. However, studies also indicate that school heads often face challenges in effectively implementing supervisory practices, such as heavy workloads, lack of training, and limited resources.

This study aims to investigate the relationship between school heads' supervisory practices and teacher performance in secondary schools. It will explore the specific supervisory practices employed by school heads and their impact on various aspects of teacher performance, including instructional delivery, classroom management, and professional development (Catherine & Andala, 2024).

In Ekiti State, Nigeria, a study was conducted by Oyebanji (2019) which examined principals' supervisory practices and the extent to which these could enhance teachers' job performance. Three hundred and Seventy teachers including the principals drawn from 20 secondary schools in 16 Local Government Areas of Ekiti State were used in the study. The finding revealed that there was a significant positive relationship between principals' supervisory practices and the teachers' job performance. Based on the finding, it was recommended that principals should therefore employ supervisory practices that will encourage the teachers to put in their best while discharging their duties. Likewise, A study carried out in Zamboanga del Norte by Delas Penas (2019) found a moderate relationship between teachers' performance and supervisory procedures. Thus, school heads were generally competent, and teachers were

performing their duties and responsibilities very satisfactorily. However, they need guidance in professional growth and development aspects. The supervisory competencies play an important role since it can be equated with the teachers' performance; hence, be emphasized in aiming for quality teachers' performance.

The researcher would like to conduct this study in this context in order to ascertain whether the performance of teachers in public secondary schools in Monkayo West District, Division of Davao de Oro, during the school year 2023–2024, is significantly correlated with the supervisory practices of school heads. The researcher notes that there are situations in which teachers become disinterested in carrying out their duties. There are complaints about their school heads specifically in dealing with them and making some decisions that are far from what is expected of them. Particularly in how they handle them and make some judgments that deviate greatly from expectations, the heads of their schools are the subject of criticism. Teachers need to remind them sometimes, but they feel embarrassed to do so. Any outcomes from this project should ideally educate the heads of the schools.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the effects of school heads' instructional supervisory practices on the performance of the teachers in public secondary schools, in Monkayo West District, Division of Davao de Oro during the School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of the school heads' instructional supervisory practices in terms of:
 - 1.1. resource provider,
 - 1.2. instructional specialist,
 - 1.3. curriculum specialist,
 - 1.4. learning facilitator, and
 - 1.5. school leader?
2. What is the performance level of the teachers based on the following:
 - 2.1. plans instruction,
 - 2.2. knowledge of the subject matter, and
 - 2.3. students' engagement?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the school heads' instructional supervisory practices and the performance of the teachers?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used the quantitative descriptive-correlational research design. The quantitative approach allowed the researcher to collect data using a survey questionnaire. Quantitative research is the process of collecting and analyzing numerical data to find patterns, make predictions, test relationships, and generalize results to wider populations (Scribbr, 2020). Furthermore, it was descriptive since this requires the careful collection, analysis and interpretation of mostly quantitative data to show the status of knowledge regarding specific variables or even described the degrees of relationship among variables using the survey questionnaire in gathering information (Castardo, 2018). Correlational design is a procedure in quantitative research of which the researcher used a correlational statistical technique to describe and measure the degree of relationship between or among the variables of the study.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 160 public secondary school teachers in Monkayo West District, Division of Davao de Oro during the school year 2023-2024. The respondents of every participating district were selected through the stratified random sampling method. This type of probability sampling technique allowed the researcher to obtain a sample population that best represents the entire population being studied. To perform the stratified sampling method, the population of respondents was listed by school before estimating the sample size required. The number of public secondary school teachers representing each respective schools in the Monkayo West District of Davao de Oro Division is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Name of School</i>	<i>Total No. of Teachers</i>	<i>Total No. of Respondents</i>
1. Anagase IS	15	9
2. Cabangkalan IS	15	9
3. Danggayon IS	12	7
4. San Isidro IS	8	5
5. Casoon NHS	13	8
6. Awao NHS	20	13
7. New Kapatagan NHS	12	7
8. Monkayo NHS	168	102
Total	263	160

Instruments

The research instrument is adapted and modified from the study of Alkrdem & Mofareh (2015). The researcher used the following instruments to gather the necessary data. The questionnaire was composed of two parts. Part I assessed the school heads' supervisory practices that were implemented in conducting the instructional supervision to teachers such as resource provider, instructional specialist, curriculum specialist, learning facilitator, and school leader. Similarly, Part II was the evaluation of teacher's performance which included the roles of teacher as plans instruction, knowledge of the subject matter and the student's engagement. The result was gathered from the teacher-respondents with the consent of the school heads.

Validation of Instrument

The validation of the instrument was done to determine whether the questionnaire measures what it was designed to measure. This allowed the researcher to ensure that every item corresponded to a desired measurement and that everything that should be measured was actually obtained. Before the questionnaire was administered to the teacher-respondents, the copies of the questionnaire were checked and validated by experts for further improvement and revisions. The comments and suggestions were the bases in the initial modification of the questionnaire. After this, the researcher asked the permission from the school heads so that the questionnaire was tested to 15 teachers who were not involved in this study. These steps were undertaken for the revisions and improvement of the questionnaire to get the accurate data.

Procedure

The researcher will complete all steps in the research procedure.

Seeking Permission to Conduct the Study. Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher will ask permissions from proper authorities that are necessary for the conduct of the study. First, before securing a clearance from Research Ethics Committee to conduct the study, the research protocol will be subjected to a full-board for the initial review and expedited for the resubmission - ethics review. Second, I will secure a clearance from the Research Ethics Committee. Then, the researcher will secure a letter of endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate school. Seeking permission to conduct the study, the researcher drafted a letter of permission together with the endorsement letter from the office of the graduate school and addressed them to the Schools Division Superintendent through HR department, Upon the approval of the letter by the Schools Division Superintendent, the researcher handed another letter to the Public School District Supervisor and to the principals where the study will be conducted. Furthermore, this study will also undergo research ethics review in the Research Ethics Committee. These permits will be secured before the researcher starts to gather data for the study so that ethical considerations (respect for persons, beneficence, justice) particularly on data privacy and its provisions will be adhered in the conduct of the study.

Administering the Questionnaire. To start the study, the questionnaire was administered to the identified teachers. And the researcher himself was the one who to administer with the appropriate cooperation of the school heads. And to facilitate clear understanding of the survey questionnaire the researcher explained clearly the items and the respondents were given enough time to answer it.

Data Gathering. Respondents were assured of the anonymity of their responses and no specific reference was made to individuals or district when the findings were revealed. Once the questionnaires were retrieved, all responses were recorded, tabulated, analyzed, and treated with utmost confidentiality. All the data was submitted to the statistician for statistical computation afterward, the researcher analyzed and interpreted for discussion.

Data Analysis

The quantification, analysis and interpretation of data were aided by the following statistical tools:

The mean and standard deviation was used to measure the central tendency of the responses and standard deviation that measures the school heads' supervisory practices and the performance level of the teachers. Moreover, to find out if the survey results were significant, Pearson-r was used to examine the significant relationship between the instructional supervisory practices and the teacher's performance.

Results and Discussion

This section discussed the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data gathered from the survey questionnaires which were answered by the teacher respondents.

School Head's Instructional Supervisory Practices

Resource Provider. Reflected in Table 2 is the level of instructional supervisory practices in terms of resource provider.

Table 2 shows the level of the school heads' instructional supervisory practices as perceived by the teachers. From the data, it was revealed that the overall mean rating of 3.26 which is described as often. This means that the teachers observed that their school heads were at all times resource provider. They were ready to provide assistance to all their teachers for effective instruction.

Table 2. *School Heads' Instructional Supervisory Practices in terms of Resource Provider*

<i>I observed that the school head...</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. demonstrates effective use of time and resources.	3.08	Often
2. plan, organizes, schedule, and prioritize work to be done.	3.16	Often
3. delegates work as appropriate.	3.16	Often
4. assigns staff members according to their strengths.	3.24	Often
5. establishes ongoing process for planning and making necessary changes within the school.	3.09	Often
6. creates a positive climate and nurture creative approaches to change.	3.57	Always
7. demonstrates the ability to motivate teachers.	3.18	Often
8. knows the teachers' strengths about instructional resources that may be helpful to them.	3.21	Often
Overall Mean	3.26	Often

In particular, the indicator creates a positive climate and nurture creative approaches to change received the highest mean rating of 3.57 described as always. This means that the school heads create and possess positive school climate. As instructional leader, school heads had created a positive climate and nurture creative approaches to improve teachers' creativity in teaching. This aligns to the study of Msuya and Mwila (2023) that effective instructional supervision by school heads is crucial for coordinating, improving, and maintaining high teaching and learning standards in schools. Indicator, demonstrate effective use of time and resources obtained the lowest mean rating of 3.08 and described as often. They do classroom observations and manage their time efficiently and made use the time and resources for instructional activities. With the descriptive interpretation as always, it signifies that the level of school heads supervisory practice performed is very evident. Moreover, it is worth to point out that the result is heterogeneous in nature because of the item number 6, creates a positive climate and nurture creative approaches to change which described as always.

Instructional Specialist. It is presented in Table 3 the level of being an instructional specialist of the head teachers.

Table 3. *School Heads' Instructional Supervisory Practices in terms of Instructional Specialist*

<i>I observed that the school head...</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. demonstrates the ability to evaluate and reinforce appropriate and effective instructional strategies.	3.31	Often
2. uses knowledge and skill in effective instructional strategies.	3.41	Often
3. supervises the teachers using strategies that focus on the improvement of instruction.	3.33	Often
4. provides teachers with evidence of continuity between clinical supervision observations.	3.40	Often
5. develops intervention procedures designed to identify strengths and remediate weaknesses.	3.27	Often
6. conducts conferences effectively with teachers regarding performance.	3.25	Often
7. knows the importance of student learning objectives to the implementation of the instructional program.	3.29	Often
8. communicates to staff and community the extent to which learning objectives for the school have been mastered.	3.26	Often
Overall Mean	3.30	Often

Table 3 presents the level of the school heads as instructional specialist. Results revealed an overall mean rating of 3.30 and described as often. This means that school heads were at often practiced as instructional specialist. They shared what they have learned, experienced, and studied. In particular, the indicator used knowledge and skill in effective instructional strategies garnered the highest mean rating of 3.41 and described as often. This means that at all times school heads showed their knowledge in providing their expertise and personal skills in achieving effective instruction. They provided instructional strategies for the teachers to learn and be more creative in teaching. This aligns to the study of Esia-Donkoh and Baffoe (2018) that the process for educational programs must be prepared, designed, directed, led, and implemented for educational goals to be met. The indicator, conduct conferences effectively with teachers regarding performance garnered the lowest mean rating of 3.25 and described as often. This means that the school heads conducted post conferences after class observations. There were discussions made between the school heads and the teachers after the classroom observations. This is important especially if the teachers being observed needed help for the improvement of their performance. With the descriptive interpretation as often, it signifies that the level of school heads supervisory practice performed is evident. Furthermore, it is worth to point out that the result is homogeneous in nature.

Curriculum Specialist. It is presented in Table 4 the level of the school heads' supervisory practices in terms of curriculum specialist.

Table 4 shows the level of being a curriculum specialist of the school heads. Results revealed an overall mean rating of 3.34 and described as often. This means that school heads have acted at all times as a curriculum specialist in their respective schools. They have provided support to teachers especially mentoring them to improve their performance in the classroom instruction. In particular, the indicator, develop and organize in-service training programs for teachers and provide continuous and effective professional development got the highest mean rating of 3.42 and described as at often. This implies that school heads regularly organized an in-service training for teachers and provide continuous and effective professional training. This aligns to the study of Ngole and Mkulu (2021) that the heads of schools, operating under the purview of these ministries, bear the responsibility of overseeing the execution of the curriculum as immediate supervisor. The indicator, focuses on knowledge, skills and ability towards curriculum improvement and staff development garnered the lowest mean rating of 3.30 and described as often. This means that the school heads focus on knowledge,

skills, and abilities is to improve staff development and the course of study as a whole.

Table 4. *School Heads' Instructional Supervisory Practices in terms of Curriculum Specialist*

<i>I observed that the school head...</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. focuses on knowledge, skills and ability towards curriculum improvement and staff development.	3.30	Often
2. displays mastery in the discussion of curriculum planning and implementation.	3.34	Often
3. guides teacher in delivering accurate and updated content knowledge using appropriate methodologies, approaches, and strategies.	3.35	Often
4. helps teacher to select, prepare, and utilize available technology and other instructional materials appropriate to the learners and the learning objectives.	3.31	Often
5. assists the teacher to align the lesson objectives, teaching methods, learning activities and instructional materials or resources appropriate to the learners.	3.42	Often
6. develops and organize in-service training programs for teachers and provide continuous and effective professional development.	3.36	Often
7. develops and use a variety of appropriate curriculum assessment strategies to monitor and evaluate teaching and learning.	3.36	Often
8. creates and utilizes appropriate instructional planning and implementation.	3.31	Often
Overall Mean	3.34	Often

There were discussions made between the school heads and the teachers about the strategies that teachers need to maintain a conducive learning environment, adjust to changing demands, and enhance their methods of instruction on a constant basis. With the descriptive interpretation as often, it signifies that the level of school heads supervisory practice performed is evident. Furthermore, it is worth to point out that the result is homogeneous in nature.

Learning Facilitator. Table 5 presents the level of supervisory practices in terms of being a learning facilitator.

Table 5. *School Heads' Instructional Supervisory Practices in terms of Learning Facilitator*

<i>I observed that the school head...</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. monitors teachers to determine instruction that include elements of effective instruction.	3.40	Often
2. engages teachers in mutual inquiry which aims for the improvement of instruction.	3.39	Often
3. shares the responsibility of the instructional supervision and teaching improvement.	3.38	Often
4. intensifies the conduct of instructional supervision to include all school aspects.	3.38	Often
5. provides teachers with an adequate amount of information to become familiar with the supervisory process.	3.36	Often
6. makes efforts to reduce teachers' level of anxieties concerning the supervisory practices.	3.35	Often
7. ensures that all teachers in the school receive supervisory feedback.	3.39	Often
8. helps teachers to identify appropriate teaching and learning processes.	3.41	Often
Overall Mean	3.38	Often

Table 5 shows the level of school heads' instructional supervisory practices in terms of learning facilitator. Results reveal an overall mean rating of 3.38 and described as often. In particular, indicator no. 8 received the highest mean rating of 3.41 and described as often. This means that school heads are very willing to mentor the teachers to select the best strategies for them. While indicator no. 6 got the lowest mean rating of 3.35 and described as often. This means that the school heads extend their assistance to help the teachers to cope with their anxieties and challenges. This aligns to the study of Msuya and Mwila (2023) that the school heads should provide opportunities for teachers to share strategies and engage in professional development, which enhances instructional skills. With the descriptive interpretation as often, it signifies that the level of school heads supervisory practice performed is evident. Moreover, it is worth to point out that the result is homogeneous in nature.

School Leader. It is indicated in the table below the level of the instructional supervisory practices of the school heads as a school leader.

Table 6 displays the level of school heads' instructional supervisory practices as a school leader. Results reveal an overall mean rating of 3.31 and described as often. This means that the school heads performed their functions very often. This implies that the school heads as a school leader did their best in making decisions that could benefit the teachers, students and other stakeholder. In particular, the indicator no. 6 got the highest mean rating of 3.37 and described as often. This means that the school heads made important decisions for the school and they take the initiative to consult stakeholders before making the final decisions. This implies that the school heads addressed some school issues and concerns and made decisions to solve such issues and concerns. This aligns to the study of Engelbrecht et al. (2017) that morally consistent, credible, and trustworthy leader can foster the feeling of trust. Leader integrity has a significantly positive influence on the trust in the leader. The indicator no. 1 got the lowest mean rating of 3.26 and described as at often. This means that the school heads emphasized on the school curriculum and instruction issues which need to be addressed. They put more priority to address the different issues and problems concerning classroom instruction which need speedy action. With the descriptive interpretation as often, it implies that the level of school heads supervisory practice performed is evident. Moreover, it is worth to point

out that the result is homogeneous in nature.

Table 6. *School Heads' Instructional Supervisory Practices As a School Leader*

<i>I observed that the school head...</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. places priority on curriculum and instruction issues.	3.26	Often
2. creates a climate of high expectations characterized by a tone of respect for teachers, students, parents, and community.	3.36	Often
3. functions as a leader with direct involvement in instructional policy by communicating the school policies.	3.34	Often
4. demonstrates commitment to academic goals, ability to develop and articulate a clear vision of long-term goals for the school.	3.31	Often
5. monitors student progress toward school achievement and teacher effectiveness in achieving goals.	3.33	Often
6. consults with others by involving the faculty and other groups in school decision processes.	3.37	Often
7. mobilizes resources such as materials, time, and support to enable the school and its personnel to meet academic goals.	3.28	Often
8. works cooperatively with the staff and the community to develop clear goals that relate to the organization's mission.	3.28	Often
Overall Mean	3.31	Often

Teacher's Performance.

Plans Instruction. It is presented in Table 7 the level of the teachers' performance in terms of Plans Instruction.

Table 7. *Plans Instruction*

<i>As a teacher, I...</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. prepare lessons relevant and aligned to the prescribed curriculum.	3.31	Very Satisfactory
2. formulate attainable learning objectives.	3.41	Very Satisfactory
3. plan activities according to the pupils' abilities.	3.49	Very Satisfactory
4. consider time available in planning.	3.36	Very Satisfactory
5. develop long-range plans and daily lessons.	3.35	Very Satisfactory
6. demonstrate flexibility in planning.	3.38	Very Satisfactory
7. choose activities, materials, and resources appropriate for pupils' needs.	3.33	Very Satisfactory
8. plan instruction based on formative and summative assessment based on learners' interest.	3.33	Very Satisfactory
Overall Mean	3.38	Very Satisfactory

Table 7 presents the level of teachers' performance. Result reveals an overall mean rating of 3.38 and described as very satisfactory. This means that the teacher-respondents demonstrated very satisfactory performance in serving the learners and the school in general. In particular, indicator no. 3 got the highest mean rating of 3.49 and described as very satisfactory. This means that the teacher-respondents are well prepared of their instructional plans. Indicator no. 1 received the lowest mean rating of 3.31 and described as very satisfactory. This means that the teacher-respondents had prepared the lessons relevant to the curriculum. They followed the recommended curriculum guide as to the topics that are considered as the most essential learning competencies prescribed by the department of Education (DepEd). This aligns to the study of Olivares-Cuhat and Rohrer (2021) that good instructional preparation is essential to teachers' success since it affects both classroom management and student outcomes. In line with, their research emphasizes that lesson plans with a clear framework help teachers stay organized and have a favorable effect on student engagement and academic performance with the descriptive interpretation as very satisfactory, it implies that the level of teacher's performance is evident. Moreover, it is worth to point out that the result is homogeneous in nature.

Knowledge of the Subject Matter. It is presented in Table 8 the level of the teachers' performance in terms of their knowledge of the subject matter.

Table 8. *Knowledge of the Subject Matter*

<i>As a teacher, I...</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. teach accurate and up-to-date information.	3.39	Very Satisfactory
2. coordinate learning content with instructional objectives.	3.35	Very Satisfactory
3. use effective examples and illustrations.	3.31	Very Satisfactory
4. present learning content in a logical sequential order.	3.36	Very Satisfactory
5. express knowledge in lesson presentation and put ideas across logically.	3.35	Very Satisfactory
6. demonstrate an understanding and take responsibility for promoting high standards of literacy.	3.40	Very Satisfactory
7. establish an awareness of developments in the subject and curriculum areas.	3.34	Very Satisfactory
8. foster and maintain students' interest in the subject being taught.	3.32	Very Satisfactory
Overall Mean	3.35	Very Satisfactory

Table 8 shows the level of the teachers’ knowledge of the subject matter. The data revealed an overall mean of 3.35 and described as very satisfactory. This means that the teachers’ knowledge of the subject matter is evident. As observed, teachers are experts on their field of specialization and mastered the subject they are handling. In particular, the indicator, I demonstrate an understanding and take responsibility for promoting high standards of literacy got the highest mean rating of 3.40 and described as very satisfactory. This means that the teacher-respondents demonstrate very high understanding and take full responsibility for promoting high standards of literacy. This aligns to the study of Jang (2019) that emphasize the significance of teachers' deep understanding of the subject matter in improving instructional practices and student learning outcomes. In connection with, Jang's research highlights that teachers with robust content knowledge are better able to facilitate meaningful learning experiences and adapt their teaching strategies to meet diverse student needs. The indicator, I use effective examples and illustrations got the lowest mean rating of 3.31 and described as very satisfactory. Although the mean rating is lowest compared to the other indicators but it still received the same description. The teachers gave examples in their discussion of the subject matter and performed illustrations for the students to understand deeply the lesson. With the descriptive interpretation as very satisfactory, it implies that the level of teacher’s performance is evident. Moreover, it is worth to point out that the result is homogeneous in nature.

Students’ Engagement. Presented in Table 9 is the teachers’ performance in terms of the students’ engagement

Table 9. *Students’ Engagement*

<i>As a teacher, I...</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. create a climate in which students display initiative and assume a personal responsibility for learning.	3.16	Very Satisfactory
2. provide opportunities for each student to meet success regularly.	3.22	Very Satisfactory
3. use evaluative feedback to determine level of skill acquisition.	3.25	Very Satisfactory
4. encourage active participation from all students.	3.35	Very Satisfactory
5. use higher order questioning techniques to promote critical thinking skills.	3.19	Very Satisfactory
6. make use of time for an effective learning with the students.	3.31	Very Satisfactory
7. formulate methods of evaluation clear and purposeful to all learners.	3.20	Very Satisfactory
8. build opportunities for conferences to discuss student progress.	3.20	Very Satisfactory
Overall Mean	3.26	Very Satisfactory

Table 9 presents the teachers’ performance in terms of the students’ engagement. Data revealed an overall mean rating of 3.26 and described as very satisfactory. This means that the teachers have high sense of responsibility. They were able to motivate the students to be part of the lesson discussion. Students are active participants during classroom activities. Their engagement with the teachers was a manifestation that they are involved and interested to learn. This would mean that the teachers were good in facilitating learning. The indicator, encourage active participation from all students got the highest mean rating of 3.35 and described as very satisfactory. This means that the teacher-respondents hold a high accountability in motivating their students to participate in the class. This implies that they were able to motivate their students to be more involved in the lesson discussion and activities. This aligns to the study of Brewer and Burgess (2022) that student engagement remains a critical indicator of effective teaching, with recent literature emphasizing its multifaceted impact on learning outcomes. In line with, Brewer and Burgess argue that fostering student engagement involves creating interactive learning environments where students feel motivated to participate actively in their own learning processes. The indicator, I create a climate in which students display initiative and assume a personal responsibility for learning got the lowest mean rating of 3.16 and described as very satisfactory. This means that the teachers created a classroom climate where the students are free to be involved in the discussion and activities. Because of this, students take their own initiative to be active participants. With the descriptive interpretation as very satisfactory, it implies that the level of teacher’s performance is evident. Moreover, it is worth to point out that the result is homogeneous in nature.

Relationship Between the School Heads’ Instructional Supervisory Practices and Teachers’ Performance

Table 10. *Relationship Between School Heads’ Instructional Supervisory Practices and the Teacher’s Performance*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Correlation coefficient</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
I/V	3.28	0.61	0.000	0.77	Significant
D/V	3.31	0.57			

Table 10 presents the result of the computation to test the relationship between the school heads’ instructional supervisory practices and teacher’s performance. It is clearly presented in the table that p-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significance which indicates that there is a significant relationship between the school heads’ instructional supervisory practices and the teachers’ performance. It is also shown in the table the correlation coefficient is 0.77 which means that there is a very high positive correlation between the independent and the dependent variable. In other words, the instructional supervisory practices of the school heads that include the resource provider, instructional specialist, curriculum specialist, learning facilitator and school leader are high which also suggest that the performance of the teachers is high. In this study it pointed out that the school heads manifested the good practices that are expected the way they managed their teachers and the whole school in general. It also means that whatever the school heads will do the teachers are affected either positively or negatively. Besides, this aligns to the study of Msuya and Mwila (2023) which expresses that the

"instructional supervision established a positive correlation with content knowledge and pedagogy" of teachers. Their study examined the relationship between school heads' supervision practices and teachers' instructional performance.

School Head's Instructional Supervisory Practices.

Resource Provider. Based on the data, it was revealed that the school heads were at all times ready to provide their expertise to the teachers as well as the students. They disseminated important teaching strategies that would improve teachers teaching skills. The school head leadership is critical to improving the workplace for teachers and in most cases, teachers had high dependence of their school leader. In this case, the school heads are good resource providers that enable them to implement instructional practices effectively. The Professional Learning Association (2021) cited that school administrators as resource providers, coaches assist teachers in locating tools, supplies, equipment, and best practice examples, as well as information on delivery of instruction, student learning evaluation, and classroom management. When a coach is attempting to get into a teacher's classroom, becoming a resource provider is often the first move. Working in this position aids in the development of trust and reputation among coaches. Thus, school heads had provided essentials concepts to enhance teachers' performance through the topics they have presented during conferences and professional gatherings.

The school heads had a very high motivation to create and possess positive school climate. This also implies that as instructional leader, school heads had created a positive climate and nurture creative approaches to improve teachers' creativity in teaching. They were hopeful to ignite teachers' interest in continuing effective teaching. As observed, school heads were always innovating and imparting their skills on improving teachers and students' capabilities and eventually possess excellent performance. Waldman (2018) stated that for students to learn, they must feel safe, engaged, connected, and supported in their classrooms and schools. These "conditions for learning" are the elements of a school's climate that students experience personally. School heads can engage and hopeful on igniting the community members, teachers, students, and parents in school climate improvement work through conversations, meetings, surveys, and creating school community partnerships.

Further, the school heads have made use the time and resources for important activities. This indicates that they need to keep tract on the educational resources for there are the things that could improve learners' academic performance. As observed, essential resources for teachers and learners were provided and utilized carefully and efficiently. The school has provided resources to help teachers and learners improve their skills. Thus, time was spent for necessary school activities.

However, as explained by Grissom, Loeb, and Mitani (2018), managing everything can seem overwhelming, with principals citing time management as one of the top three challenges of their jobs. School principals often find their time eaten up by necessary but less important tasks and activities. Generally, teachers valued their school heads for the efficient time management and as resource provider of the essential materials and needs in school. School heads had emphasized that they need to demonstrate effective time administration and resources utilization for these were necessary in the observance of real leadership and management. Better time management can be achieved if goals have been set and then all future work is prioritized based on how it moves the individual or organization towards meeting the goals.

Furthermore, Victor (2018) supported and added that setting target for meetings, ensuring timely converge of scheme of work, delegation of duties to teachers and students scheduling extra-curricular activities among others are characteristics of time management of school leaders. Moreover, as posited by Mutisya (2018), in terms of resource mobilization, school principals should be constantly trained on financial resource mobilization so that they can be effective in financial mobilization and management.

Instructional Specialist. Results revealed that the school heads performed as an instructional specialist. They shared what they have learned, experienced, and studied. This made them more admirable and inspiring. This indicates that they were considered as provider of best practices in education. They really believed that school heads were adept and expert in instructional practices and undertakings. As opined by Duffy (2018), it is a natural way for school leaders to take on the role of instructional leader is to serve as a chief coach for teachers through developing and implementing effective instructional coaching at the classroom level. School principals are responsible for acting as instructional leaders through promoting best practices in teaching and learning so that students achieve academic success.

Moreover, principals were involved in many tasks that tend to distract from this goal, but effective principals focus on instructional supervision for these benefit the teachers and learners. Pitpit (2020) cited that instructional leadership is a condition where school leaders focus on instruction to improve student achievement. They need to perform effectively as an instructional leader. They need to know various instructional strategies which they can impart and suggest to teachers what they have observed with the end goal of improving learner's performance. School principals' responsibilities are complicated in terms of making decisions and meeting new demands, but school principals' primary function is to manage teaching and learning (Mestry, 2018).

Teachers were provided with teaching strategies during instructional supervision and observation. As supported by Toch (2019), instructional leadership of a school principal is a significant factor in facilitating, improving, and promoting the academic progress of students. This means school administrators should make time to get into the classrooms. At the very least, set aside a couple of hours per day to observe and collaborate with teachers. They will mainly do conferences to focus on the things a teacher needs to emphasize during demonstrations and essentially the performance of the students. School principals and teachers should manage parent relations

for learners' academic performance. Principals also need to find ways to reward excellence in their classrooms through leadership opportunities and promotions. Outstanding teachers are motivated by professional recognition and this will lead them for promotion. As such, students' academic should be focused on principals' time with the teachers.

Curriculum Specialist. Results reveal that the school heads are performing as curriculum specialists in their respective schools. This implies that they have provided support to teachers. This further indicates that they have helped create and revise instructional resources used in the classroom. As noticed, they assessed the school's implementation and evaluation of instruction and resources. Thus, they were aware that they the responsible persons to motivate their teachers to be effective facilitator of learning.

As speculated by Brouse (2020), curriculum is a roadmap to instruction, but it can certainly take some experience to use it with ease as a classroom teacher or as school administrators. Many schools have curriculum specialists, whose primary role is to help teachers implement the curriculum in a way that meets the needs of all learners, but this role encompasses so much more. Curriculum specialists are teacher-leaders or school heads. Due to their experience and success in the classroom and in school they serve as collaborators and guides for classroom teachers to plan lessons, analyze student performance, model instruction, support differentiation, and so much more. In particular, the school heads regularly organized in-service training for teachers and provide continuous and effective professional training. This indicates that school heads wanted to develop teacher's personal and professional qualities and improve their knowledge, skills, and practices leading to the improvement of the academic performance of the students. As observed, school heads were particular in enhancing and developing teachers so they can have extraordinary achievements that could be utilized for promotion and self-growth.

As stated by Shanmugavelu (2018) in-service training acted as a catalyst for teacher's effectiveness. It is also a way of updating teachers' skills and knowledge for improving teaching and learning which lead to better job performance and it is a fundamental aspect to improve teacher professionalism. Moreover, the school heads took active role in shaping the school curriculum. They focus on enhancing teachers' subject knowledge, skills, and abilities towards curriculum. This indicates that they are responsible in the formulation of the schools' vision, philosophy, mission and objectives. Noticeably, school heads have invested resources, skills, and knowledge to provide necessary leadership in evaluating teaching personnel and school curriculum.

As opined by Jorgensen (2018), the school principal has a key role in the overall school culture and direction. The principal was key in terms of quality curriculum but inclusive of the overall school environment and support mechanisms within the school. Hence, in this idea, it is clear that school principals are empowered to effectively implement the curriculum. The school principals may also involve some teachers in the curriculum planning so that these teachers are also informed as to how they can effectively cascade the curriculum in their co-teachers.

Learning Facilitator. Results revealed that the school heads took a very high role as a learning facilitator in their schools. They served as learning facilitator as an agent of teaching and learning process. This indicates that school heads primarily focused on the instructional aspect in relation to teachers' teaching obligations. As noticed, school heads as learning facilitator guided their teachers to be effective facilitators of learning. As posited by Pitpit (2020), school principals need to provide instructional support to teachers in the classrooms when conducting classroom observations, which can improve their teaching practices. Furthermore, Amtu, Shalla, and Tallak, (2019) added that for school principals to influence teacher creativity effectively and eventually enhance instruction, they must perform their leadership roles consciously. Teachers need support from their principals by implementing professional leadership and management practices that are geared toward achievement.

Furthermore, it was also found out that the school heads helped their teachers to be more effective communicator of learning and provide them strategies that can help the teachers to teach effectively.

As supported by Chen (2018), teachers can improve their professional abilities through principals' instructional supervision and their own knowledge management behaviors to benefit students. School heads as instructional facilitators focused on concept knowledge, skills, and empowering teachers' abilities to positively develop a culture of excellence. As added by Inclusive School Network (2015), principals play a key role in the delivery of quality instruction. They are responsible for ensuring that instructional policies that promote effective learning for all students are in place. Good principals recognize the importance of higher test scores, but also recognize the importance of high-quality instruction in raising student achievement. Principals support instructional activities and programs by modeling expected behaviors, participating in staff development, and consistently prioritizing instructional concerns on a day-to-day basis. They strive to protect instructional time by removing issues that would detract teachers from their instructional responsibilities.

Moreover, principals in effective schools are involved in instruction and work to provide resources that keep teachers focused on student achievement. They are knowledgeable about curriculum and instruction and promote teacher reflection about instruction and its effect on student achievement (Cotton, 2019).

In addition, the data also revealed that the school heads have very high technical assistance that helped teachers to cope with their anxieties and challenges on supervisory practices at all times. This implies that they have made assistance for the teachers not to be burdened with the instructional direction. This indicates also that providing mechanism to lessen anxieties related to classroom management and instruction should be one of the priorities of school leaders. As noticed, teachers were prone into stress and anxieties and providing assistance or mechanism should be extended by the school administrators so educators could excellently perform their

duties and responsibilities.

Similarly, Hoque, Kenayathulla, Subramaniam and Islam (2020) stated that classroom observations can cause stress, discomfort, and nervousness. But in the context of the present study, the school heads assist teachers not to feel that kind of discomfort, that is, they viewed it as a form of professional development. Major findings suggest that teacher burnout may result from several factors such as educational mandates, classroom discipline issues; it affects classroom instruction and impacts interaction with all educational stakeholders. Generally, school heads primarily stand as instructional facilitator to help teachers become more operative and driven in the teaching field. School heads aspire for positive social change to eliminate anxieties and retain highly qualified and motivated teachers who will provide students with consistent, high-quality, and equal educational opportunities. School heads as learning facilitators helped students reach their full academic potential through the consistent provision of teachers' different teaching strategies used and time spent for remediation.

School Leader. The data revealed that the school heads are functioning well as a school leader at all times. This implies that the school heads as a school leader did their best and made changes for the good of the school and carried out decisions that will benefit the school and all stakeholders. This further implies that as school leaders, it is their responsibility to model desirable practices, services and make changes. As noticed, effective school leaders inevitably shine and make those people around them to perform better.

As explained by Just Ask Publications and Professional Development (2021), school principals as leaders made significant part on dealing with changes that may occur in the future. While some teachers are taking a break from their jobs, the relative calm and quiet in the building afford the principal time to reflect on any impending changes and how best to implement those changes. Change is recognized as unavoidable and ongoing in the world at large. School heads focus on explosion in technology, strategies, innovations, and numerous social changes. Shift in education still seems to come as a surprise, accompanied by some resistance and trepidation. Since student learning, behavior, and motivation are so complex and unpredictable, teachers should take actions and emphasize truly the importance of achievement.

It was also revealed that the school heads were good planners and that they were able to make decisions for the teachers, students and the whole school in general. As noticed, school heads presented different situations and options on diverse issues related to school challenges. The issues were brought to the teachers for discussion and offering of conceivable clarifications in a win-win option which was a product of self-reflection and group decision process.

According to Nixon (2018), school principals may engage in a period of self-reflection to explore how previous job experiences may impact their current role as school leader. Personal bias towards students may impact how decisions are made and a principal should learn to focus on decision making at an individual level and not based on broad generalizations of students. The principal may choose to establish a team of professionals who can review data to assist in the planning process. This team should be diverse in order to have the widest possible range of viewpoints in this process. Finally, a principal should model a growth mentality by reviewing recent studies on adult and peer relationship building and engaging faculty and peers in discussions about how to create and foster healthy relationships.

The school heads had put premium on the school curriculum and instruction. The school heads prioritized the school curriculum and instruction which is very important component in the school. As theorized by Chen (2018), school principals not only play administrative roles but also instruct teachers. In order to positively affect teachers' quality, school principals must engage teachers in ways that support improved practice and seek to empower teachers as creative and innovative. Hence, by looking into curriculum and instructional issues and providing solutions by having constant dialogue with teachers, school heads are on the right track of successfully implementing the curriculum and performed their role as an instructional leader effectively and efficiently. School leaders play an increasingly important role in establishing and ensuring well-functioning 21st-century learning environments. School leaders often act as the bridge between teachers, students, parents or guardians, and the education system. Effective school leaders provide the instructional leadership to help students succeed in school and create a collaborative school environment in which teachers take part in school decision making (Schleicher, 2018).

Plans Instruction. The teachers have demonstrated very satisfactory performance in serving the school and the learners. This implies further that teachers need to improve their instructional strategies to obtain the outstanding rating. As observed, teachers' planning for the classroom was part of educating and behavior management. Proper classroom planning will keep teachers organized and on track while teaching, thus allowing them to teach more and manage less. Munthe and Conway (2018) cited that instructional planning can be regarded in technical terms, as a way to ensure effective classroom performance, but it can also be regarded as a means for professional learning and for curriculum development. Teachers foresee and build the context and atmosphere in which students learn as they prepare lessons. In repeated cycles of preparation, enactment, evaluation, and re-planning, they align priorities, tasks, and evaluations. The result revealed that the school heads considered their pupils prior before they plan their instructional activities. This also indicates that they really valued their pupils and they made possible interventions on the challenged individuals inside the classroom. Noticeably, teachers had set the lesson objectives which were achievable by all the pupils at different levels. The learning objectives and the learning outcomes must be differentiated in such a way so as to take into consideration and value all pupils' talents and needs.

As explained by Finley (2018), differentiated instruction is one answer that has been extensively documented and would always be part of teachers' instructional plan. This will definitely suit students' diverse abilities at this 21st Century education. Differentiation is a method of instruction that adjusts what students learn (content), how they accumulate information (process), how they demonstrate knowledge or skills (product), and with whom and where they learn to meet the needs of all students (learning environment). Differentiation is not just a set of instructional methods. Rather, it is a way of thinking about teaching and learning to ensure that children receive appropriate classroom experiences. As opined by De Meij and Merx (2018), curriculum alignment is crucial in realizing learning objectives. Teachers made it to a point that the objectives, activities and the assessment tasks they prepared were consistent with the existing curriculum. A more productive and effective regular teaching would benefit from a more aligned curriculum structure. It will make it easier for teachers to create meaningful integrated learning by bundling standards. In order for learning objectives to become actual learning outcomes, and therefore to optimize students' learning, it is important to make sure every activity helps to realize the learning objectives. Instructional plans have a crucial function in helping teachers participate in the planning of instructional practices, which enables teachers to create a unique design for their own students. Student-centered approaches make it necessary that the curriculum programs should be dynamic and be designed in a shape that is conducive to further development and modifications during the implementation process (Galton, 2018). The process of curriculum development does not end with the preparation of curriculum programs; it continues with the teachers' instructional planning activities, finalizing with the actual delivery of the instruction in the classroom.

However, the findings of Özpölat and Bay (2018) were in disagreement with the importance of curriculum alignment when planning the lesson. They found out that teachers did not adhere to the original form of the curriculum during the teaching process, and they administered differently. Another thought-provoking situation on this was none of the teachers' not regarding curriculum alignment despite carrying on their duties in schools with different success levels. The teacher uses knowledge of subject areas, curriculum, cross-disciplinary skills, and pedagogy, as well as knowledge of learners and the group background, to prepare instruction that helps every student achieve rigorous learning goals. Generally, teachers were consistent on their obligation as instructional planner. They have planned activities according to their pupils' abilities and capabilities. They were observant of the need in extending their expertise to learners. They have prepared lessons relevant and aligned to the prescribed curriculum which made them more effective and inspiring to the learners. They have valued open-mindedness with their students and made sure that learners will have meaningful academic journey with them. Indeed, they made a difference!

Knowledge of the Subject Matter. Results revealed that the teachers are knowledgeable what to teach. They have enough knowledge in imparting on the different lessons as seen in the curriculum. This indicates that if teachers are knowledgeable of the curriculum, they can better serve the learners. Noticeably, a good curriculum also connects teachers from across grade levels and subject areas to look at the big picture of student learning. Teachers should collaborate to prepare a series of topics that expand on previous ones and interact across disciplines. According to Niemelä and Tirri (2018), curriculum knowledge means teachers' broad comprehension of school subjects and an understanding that the current one presents only one way of constructing a curriculum. Knowledge of various instructional materials, teaching methods, and learning goals are all part of the curriculum. Integrative instruction's goal is to help students see the connections and inter-dependencies between the phenomena to be studied. It helps the pupils to link knowledge of and skills in various fields, and in interaction with others, to structure them as meaningful entities. Teachers possess knowledge on different fields to be applied to learners and produce experiences of participation in the communal building of knowledge. This encourages students to understand the importance of the subjects they study in school about their own lives and communities, as well as for society and humanity as a whole. In the learning process, pupils are supported to structure and expand their worldview where teachers are vital factors in equipping them with desirable learning as a product of teachers' subject knowledge.

The teachers are very good in presenting, illustrating and discussing the concepts based on the most essential competencies. This implies that teachers need to consistently perform excellent styles in discussing the lessons. This further indicates that instructional resources will help teachers demonstrate the precise competencies. As observed, teachers were using examples and illustrations to effectively discuss a concept for better learning and understanding. They were very creative in elaborating information and illustrations. Illustrations were powerful ways to broaden and deepen student learning.

As stressed by Alford and Griffin (2019), integrating meaningful learning examples and concept illustrations should take place at all levels of teaching. As such, students learn through explanation, example, and experience they get in the classroom. Even after accounting for previous student learning and family history characteristics, teacher consistency is a significant factor in evaluating increases in student achievement. Teacher quality is congruent to the pedagogical knowledge of teachers on a curriculum. Teachers' advanced expertise for designing productive teaching and learning environments for all students is referred to as pedagogical knowledge. The use of resources better improves learners understanding of the lesson and allows comprehension. Through creating illustrations children learn not only to look more closely at their subject but also to communicate the results of their queries, experiments, observation, research, scientific facts and theories to others. Generally, teachers were capable of disseminating subject knowledge and content. They have demonstrated an understanding and take responsibility for promoting high standards of literacy inside the classroom. They were adept and innovative in presenting the topics. They have made and delivered interventions for students' academic growth and excellent performance. They have used effective examples and illustrations to better implement the most essential competencies which the learners deserve to acquire for lifelong learning.

Curriculum experience, according to Tirri (2018), requires knowledge of different instructional materials, teaching methods, and learning objectives. Teachers also use a variety of curricular resources from which to choose appropriate methods. It is critical that teachers understand that they have the option of using other resources, that alternative learning approaches are accessible, and that there are various options.

Students' Engagement. Results revealed that the teachers are responsible and they took their role as one of the most important factors of students' achievement. This implies that teachers were very consistent in developing students to achieve better performance. The primary concern of the teachers is to serve the school and one their priorities is extending knowledge for students' meaningful and learning achievements. As noticed, teachers have delivered different strategies and methodologies to help learners developed their full potentials. They served with passion, commitment and dedication. They have valued each learner and were hopeful of the desirable and reasonable academic performance. As a matter of fact, according to Goldhaber (2018), the quality of teachers shows a stronger relationship than school facilities and curricula to pupil achievement. Hence, it is imperative that DepEd should hire teachers who are qualified for the job and possess the needed skills of the teacher to promote student achievement. The teachers hold a high accountability in motivating their students to participate in the class. They need active involvement of learners to fully understand the subject and gain evocative experience. This indicates also that teachers were motivating students to give their best as they explore several experiences and learning inside the classroom. As noticed, teachers were naturally engaging learners to develop their academic potentials and creativity. Teachers were equipped with strategies in providing intrinsic and extrinsic motivations. Teachers should develop rapport and better relationship with their students to increase participation and desirable experience.

According to Schritter (2018), students that regularly participate in class are constantly involved with the material and are more likely to remember a greater portion of the information. However, the teacher's attitude toward his or her students can dramatically affect class participation in one direction or another. Students are more likely to participate in class if they have a comfortable relationship with their teacher. Hence, teachers can increase class participation by creating a safe and respectful class environment.

Relationship between the School Heads Supervisory Practices and Teacher's Performance. Results reveal school heads supervisory practices in terms of resource provider, instructional specialist, curriculum specialist, learning facilitator, and school leaders showed significant relationship with the teachers' performance. According to Manaseh (2018), instructional leadership is a kind of school leadership that is focused on teaching or instruction. It means prioritizing instructional practices over managerial duties that is, being in the classroom talking to learners and discussing their work, asking them questions about their studies and how they are helped. As an instructional leader, the school head need to advocate for effective teaching by providing clarity and support for teachers as well as procuring the necessary resources to maximize teaching effectiveness. Furthermore, Manaseh emphasized that the methods used included taking rounds, observing classrooms, using reflective diaries and taking feedback from students and their parents. School success and students' academic achievements are interrelated; therefore, the school head has the responsibility to be an instructional leader which is important for school heads to create an environment of cooperation in the school.

Conclusions

Instructional supervisory practices of school heads essentially impact teachers' performance. The instructional supervisory practices of the school heads fortunately promote collaboration and positive teachers' performance. Teachers as the facilitators of learning should be guided with the best instructional practices of their school heads. Teachers understand that supervision facilitates their professional growth and improves their teaching performance.

On the basis of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby forwarded:

The Department of Education may continue to regularly train school heads, specifically those who are newly installed school heads on effective instructional supervisory practices.

Curriculum Implementation Division Experts should consistently monitor and provide suggestions through professional training that will be conducted for the school heads. Through this the school heads together with the teachers will be constantly reminded of those essential things needed for the school to achieve their instructional goals.

It is important for school heads to continually update themselves on the best practices of instructional supervision. School heads need to encourage their teachers to grow professionally and apply for promotion in rank so that they will be satisfied with their work. Moreover, the instructional supervisory plan designed in this study may also be tried out and test its effectiveness in improving the teachers' performance.

Teachers need to be trained regularly on the effective integration of technology in the classroom as well as in implementing their lessons in such a way that would foster better learning outcomes. They should constantly employ technology-related teaching strategies and differentiated instruction to become globally competent.

Parallel studies may be conducted by future researchers but considering the perception of other stakeholders such as the school heads themselves as well as the parents.

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